

ADDRESSING PEOPLE IN ENGLISH AND USING OF THEM IN ARTHUR KONAN DOYLE'S SHERLOCK HOLMES

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Anotation: *When we talk about people we can address them. Addressing People is related to a specific kind of situation. Addressing people also can show the time of the speech. In this article There are given and discussed some types of addressing people, their meaning, types and how to use of them .*

Key words: *first name, surname, title, addressing man, addressing woman, particular woman, family status, single woman, married woman, formal address.*

Since English is a language, rather than a culture, it is difficult to teach English learners exactly how to address people. There will always be some people and some professions that require more formality than others. Addressing people in writing has different rules and formalities than in speaking.

You might not be the only person wondering about titles. Students, colleagues or acquaintances may not know what to call you. If they seem unsure about how to pronounce your name, or you want them to call you something more casual, help them out:

-Please, call me [first name]

-You can call me [nickname or short form]

There are two tyoes of addressing in english.

1.formal

2.Informal

In business situations, use formal titles unless the people you meet tell you otherwise. To get someone's attention you can say: "Excuse me, Sir" or "Pardon me, Madam/Ma'am." To greet someone you can say: "Hello Sir" or "Good morning, Madam/Ma'am." Here are the formal titles English speakers use:

Sir (adult male of any age)

Ma'am (adult female - North American)

Madam (adult female)

Mr + last name (any man)

Mrs + last name (married woman who uses her husband's last name)

Ms + last name (married or unmarried woman; common in business)

Miss + last name (unmarried woman)

Dr + last name (some doctors go by Dr + first name)

Professor + last name (in a university setting)

I am going to show some example of them in Konan Doyle's "Sherlock Holmes" . We met some instance of Dr and Mr in the first section Mr. Sherlock Holmes, part 1, The book of "A Study In Scarlet" :

Chapter I. Mr. Sherlock Holmes

"Dr. Watson, Mr. Sherlock Holmes," said Stamford, introducing us.

"How are you?" he said cordially, gripping my hand with a strength for which I should hardly have given him credit. "You have been in Afghanistan, I perceive."

Here Stamford adress to Watson and Sherlock Holmes in order to show with the other person to provide their status or position in.

Next usage is:

"Commissionaire, sir," he said, gruffly. "Uniform away for repairs."

"And you were?" I asked, with a slightly malicious glance at my companion.

"A sergeant, sir, Royal Marine Light Infantry, sir. No answer? Right, sir."

He clicked his heels together, raised his hand in a salute, and was gone.

You can easily differ from the period of speech from this passage.

There is written example too in Chapter III. The Lauriston Garden Mystery.

"My dear Mr. Sherlock Holmes: "There has been a bad business during the night at 3, Lauriston Gardens, off the Brixton Road. Our man on the beat saw a light there about two in the morning, and as the house was an empty one, suspected that something was amiss. He found the door open, and in the front room, which is bare of furniture, discovered the body of a gentleman, well dressed, and having cards in his pocket bearing the name of 'Enoch J. Drebber, Cleveland, Ohio, U.S.A.' There had been no robbery, nor is there any evidence as to how the man met his death. There are marks of blood in the room, but there is no wound upon his person. We are at a loss as to how he came into the empty house; indeed, the whole affair is a puzzler. If you can come round to the house any time before twelve, you will find me there. I have left everything in statu quo until I hear from you. If you are unable to come I shall give you fuller details, and would esteem it a great kindness if you would favour me with your opinion. "Yours faithfully,

"Tobias Gregson."

Here is "my dear" and "Yours Faithfully" written form of addressing people.

However, we can also use "my dear" in as spoken language and we can touch with on Sherlock Holmes:

"My dear fellow, what does it matter to me. Supposing I unravel the whole matter, you may be sure that Gregson, Lestrade, and Co. will pocket all the credit. That comes of being an unofficial personage."

"But he begs you to help him."

One of adressing woman is:

“My name is Sawyer—her's is Dennis, which Tom Dennis married her—and a smart, clean lad, too, as long as he's at sea, and no steward in the company more thought of; but when on shore, what with the women and what with liquor shops—”

“Here is your ring, Mrs. Sawyer,” I interrupted, in obedience to a sign from my companion; “it clearly belongs to your daughter, and I am glad to be able to restore it to the rightful owner.”

Here was known that Sawyer is not single woman but she is married woman.

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